

BENEFIT-COST RATIO AND THE CONDITION OF CONSUMERS' SURPLUS FROM RECREATIONAL PUBLIC PARK IN NEPAL

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Abstract: *This paper investigates the benefit-cost ratio and the condition of consumer surplus from recreational public parks in Nepal. The main objective of this study is to estimate the recreational benefits of Tikapur Banglaw Park (TBP), calculate consumers' surplus per visitor per trip of individual visitors and estimate benefit cost-ratio of the Park. The Individual Travel Cost Method (ITCM) has been employed to capture the non-market benefits of the Park. The study is based on the survey of 108 visitors of TBP administered during the period spanning from mid-March to mid-April 2016. The Poisson regression model has been used to estimate the consumer surplus of the visitors. The study shows that the visit rate of the Park is inversely correlated with the travel cost and age of the visitors and is positively correlated with the household income of the visitors. The mean consumer's surplus per visitor per trip is estimated to be about NPR 2475. The aggregated consumer surplus for the annual park visitors is calculated to be NPR 351 million. The estimated opportunity cost of the Park in terms of agricultural production is about NPR 8.85 million per annum. The total benefit is NPR 355 million and total cost is NPR 13 million. The benefit cost ratio is 27.43. The study finds that the Tikapur Banglaw Park generates significantly higher level of public welfare. Therefore, Tikapur Municipality should formulate a timely project intervention to upgrade the quality of TBP.*

Keywords: *non-market valuation, individual travel cost method, consumer surplus, count data, poisson regression model*

JEL Classification: C31, D01, D11, D61, Q26, Q56

Introduction

Public recreation parks are part of environmental goods and services and contribute substantially to the growth of tourism sector, thereby contributing to net value addition to any society and economy as a whole. Public Parks also significantly improve the surrounding environment by increasing greenery, reducing air, water and noise pollution, and helping in wildlife preservation (Ahmed & Gotoh, 2006). Since environmental goods and services are not traded in the usual markets; the benefits derived from these commodities are external to the market (De & Devi, 2011). There is an increasing and widespread public support for the public park provision in

urban areas given that they provide an array of different recreational activities enhancing the citizen's quality of life (Salazar & Defranesco, 2005). In other words, public parks generate high value for human welfare but they do not receive due consideration in the public policy.

Economists have developed a non-market valuation technique to estimate the benefits of environmental public goods. The technique originated in the 1940s. The proposal of Ciriacy-Wantrup (1947) to use stated preference methods to value natural resources and the environment, in addition to the idea of Hotelling (1949) to use travel costs to value economic benefits of national parks, are the pioneering work on environment valuation (ADB, 2013). In fact, there are basically two methods of valuation of the environmental goods: the market-based approach and the non-market-based approach. When a market exists, it is relatively easy to apply market-based techniques to measure the value. But when market information relating to price and quantities is not available to estimate the value of the resources or services, we use non market valuation methods. The most widely recognized nonmarket technique is Travel Cost Method (TCM) (Bhusal, 2009). TCM has been developed in order to estimate social benefits from a recreational site (Rosato & Defrancesco, 2002). There are two basic approaches to TCM: the Zonal Travel Cost Method (ZTCM) and the Individual Travel Cost Method (ITCM). The latter can be considered a refinement or a generalization of ZTCM. ITCM was developed by Brown and Nawas (1973) and Gom and Martin (1974), and it estimates the consumers' surplus by analyzing an individual visitor's behaviour and the cost sustained for the recreational activities (Rosato *et al.*, 2002).

The theory related to TCM and its application is relatively straightforward. It is grounded in the microeconomic theory of consumer behaviour which states that an individual consumer maximizes his/her utility derived from the consumption of goods and services subject to his/her budget constraints. A general solution to this constrained maximization problem yields the Marshallian demand function. The application of this microeconomic theory of consumer behaviour is relatively straightforward when private goods and services have been dealt with. This analogy, however, can be extended to public goods and services such as public parks and other recreational services. In this special case, a representative individual visitor to a recreation site, who faces budgetary and time constraints, is thought of as a consumer of a marketable goods and an environmental goods or recreational goods and services, namely visits to a recreational public park (denoted as v_i) and all other private goods and services (denoted as x_i). Let's assume that x_i and v_i represent a

vector of private marketable goods and a vector of recreational non-marketable goods respectively. Let again assume that the prices of these two goods are p_x and p_v respectively. The representative consumer can therefore spend his or her income (denoted as Y_i) on the purchase of these two sets of goods. Hence, the budget constraint of the individual visitors is given as:

$$Y_i = w T_w = p_x x_i + p_v v_i \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Y is the income level of the individual consumer i , w is the hourly wage rate and T is the total number of hours worked. The individual visitor also faces a time constraint as he or she must decide on how much time to spend on his work and leisure (recreation).

Similar to equation (1) above, the time constraint can then be stated as:

$$T = T_w + T_L \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

T is the total time endowment of the consumer and T_L is time devoted to leisure (recreation). It is to be noted that the quality of recreational sites is the key to the visitor's choice of the site.

If we denote the quality yardsticks of a recreational site as q_j then the utility function of the representative visitor can be expressed as:

$$U_{ij} = U(x_i v_i q_j) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

By maximizing equation (3) subject to equation (1) and (2), ordinary or Marshallian demand function for private marketable goods and non-market recreational goods are obtainable as:

$$X_{ij} = U(P_x P_v Y_i q_j) \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

$$V_{ij} = U(P_x P_v Y_i q_j) \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

Equation (4) and (5) represent the ordinary demand functions of marketable private goods and non-marketable recreational goods, respectively. However, the focus of this work is on the latter. It is difficult to measure the flow of the recreational services (Sarker & Surry, 2004), so, as a consequence, the number of trips to the recreational site is used as surrogates. Therefore equation (5) is crucial in computing the consumer surplus (CS) per trip and its coefficient is estimated using an appropriate econometric tool as per the nature of data of dependent variable of this study.

Limae *et al.* (2014) concluded that there is a significant relation between the number of visitors as a dependent variable and the travel cost: that is, when the travel

cost increases, the number of visitors decreases. Mathew *et al.* (2013) showed that the consumer surplus value per trip for the Langkawi model €6993 is greater than for the Kilim models (€1437 and €633) for the Poisson regression analysis. Roussel *et al.* (2012) found the mean consumer surplus at US \$ 78.03 per visitor per trip.

De and Devi (2011) estimated the consumer surplus per domestic tourist per visit to be Rs. 1787.46. The same for the foreign tourist is about Rs 15872. The revised consumer surpluses based on the additional willingness to pay are Rs. 1933.15 and Rs. 17292 i.e., there is an incremental consumer surplus of Rs. 145.69 and Rs. 1420 respectively. Nde (2011) found out that consumer surplus estimates that are equivalent to the recreational value of the beach per trip per visitor per day ranged from €2.56 to €41.51. Also, a possible access fee to the beach of €2.0 was suggested based on the visitors' stated willingness to pay. Aryal (2008) found that the total annual consumer surplus or economic benefit obtained from recreation in Chitawan National Park remained approximately at NPR 23 million (US\$ 3,421,162.7). Based on the willingness to pay, the study recommended that a Park entrance fee of US\$ 15 per person be introduced, which could be utilized for Park management. Ahmed and Gotoh (2006) showed that the residents of the Nagasaki City were willing to pay in total 920 million yen (5,225 yen per household) for preserving the public parks in the city. The negative relationship between the persons visiting the public parks and the WTP as revealed from the multivariate analysis, indicated that, the non-use value of public parks in Nagasaki City was also very high. Salazar, and Menendez (2005) found that the mean value of willingness to pay (WTP) is considerably higher for people who live closer to the planned park as it is more accessible to them.

Himayatullaha and Siddiqui (2003) found the actual consumer surplus per visitor per trip to be at Rs. 240 whereas the total actual consumer surplus was estimated to be Rs. 24.2 million. The annual consumer surplus in case of an improved scenario was projected at Rs. 35.01 million. Shrestha *et al.* (2002) estimated the CS value ranging from \$540.54 to \$869.57 per trip resulting in the total social welfare estimate in the range of \$35 to \$56 million. Adamowicz *et al.* (1989) approximated the expected values for the semilog and linear models at \$2971.14 and \$ 1601.12 respectively.

Although the findings mentioned above mostly relate to similar researches conducted in a foreign country, such findings are indicative of the nature of research undertaken in the specific context of Nepal. In this research, Tikapur Banglaw Park (TBP), a Public Park managed by Tikapur Municipality in Kailali district of Far-western Nepal, has been selected as a case to carry out the economic valuation of the public parks in Nepal.

Data and methodology

This is a small descriptive cross-sectional study and is based on single contact with the visitors of Tikapur Banglaw Park (TBP). The study area was public recreational park of Tikapur Municipality named Tikapur Banglaw Park (TBP). The popularity of the park and the researcher's convenience and accessibility to it for data collection have been taken into consideration for the selection. It is located on the easternmost edge of Kailali District and on the bank of Karnali River and about 20 Kilometers south of East West National Highway of Nepal. The TBP is spread over 58.02 hectares of land but the core park area is limited to 6.12 hectare, and it remains covered by natural forest (Tikapur Municipality, 2014). It has been the centre of attraction to a large number of tourists for last couple of years. The fascinating location of TBP at the bank of Karnali River provides ample opportunities for visitors to entertain themselves. Furthermore, it provides them with the opportunities of swimming, boating, rafting and picnicking as well. Likewise, it has a magnificent flower garden endowed with varieties of flowers that attracts substantial number of visitors annually.

This study is based on a survey of TBP visitors conducted by the researcher. The primary data was collected using a structured questionnaire. The secondary data was collected from concerned authorities like Tikapur Municipality, Agriculture Service Centre Tikapur, and Ministry of Agriculture Development of Nepal. The survey was conducted during mid-March to mid-April of 2016. This season is the peak season for park visitors after winter. The structured questionnaire covered the caste and ethnicity of visitors, place of residence, income, family size, age, gender, education, employment status, travel cost, substitute site travel cost, satisfaction from the park, the maximum amount willing to pay as entry fee. The variables were chosen to cover the objectives. This study carried out economic valuation of recreational benefit of TBP as a Public Park to infer the social benefit bestowed by the park. This study was conducted employing individual travel cost method which is popular under Revealed Preference Method. Because of the count data nature of dependent variables in this study, Poisson regression model was adopted as it better estimates the recreational benefits of the site.

Travel Cost Method (TCM) enables us to assess an individual's preferences for the consumption of non-market goods like recreational parks. It is the cost of travelling to a recreational site to reap the recreational benefits provided by the site. It is the total cost incurred in reaching the site. The TCM is a revealed preference method in which the visitors' travel costs to a recreational site are used as a proxy for the value of

recreation at that site and their visitation rates shows the amount of recreation they purchased (Navrud & Mungatana, 1994).

Econometric specification of model in functional form

According to Garrod and Willis (1999), the individual travel cost methods (ITCM) trip generating function can be define as:

$$V_{ij} = f (T_{cij}, Y_i, T_{mij}, Q_i, S_j) \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

Where, V = visit rate of individual 'i' to site 'j'.

T_{cij} = Travel cost incurred by individual 'i' when visiting site j

Y_i = Household income of individual 'i'

T_{mij} = Time cost incurred by individual 'i' when visiting site 'j'

Q_i = Vector of perceived qualities for the individual 'i'

S_j = Vector of the characteristics of available substitute sites

Model for the consumers surplus

The consumers' surplus is the differences between what an individual is willing to pay at most and what was actually paid for the use of a resource. According to Garrod and Willis (1999), consumer surplus can be defined as:

$$\text{Average Consumer Surplus per visitors per visit} = \frac{-1}{\beta} \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Where, β = Coefficient for Total travel cost estimated in the model

Equation 8 will estimate the average consumer surplus or mean consumer surplus per visitor per trip. To be able to get the aggregated consumer surplus, the average consumer surplus is multiplied by the total number of visitors to the site during a specific time period.

Econometric specification of the model in stochastic form

The model for trip generation function given in equation (2) has been generalized for Individual Travel Cost Method (ITCM) as proposed by Himayatullah *et al.* (2003) in which three dummy variables were also incorporated to fulfill, an objectives of this study as given in equation (4). In other words, the basic model used in this study depicts the number of visits to TBP as a function of factors such as travel cost, time spent in travelling substitutes sites, income, education, age, sex, place of residence and family size. Thus, the model has been estimated using econometric model as follows:

$$V_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 TC_i + \beta_2 Y_i + \beta_3 STC + \beta_4 A_i + \beta_5 E_i + \beta_6 FS_i + \beta_7 + \sum_k \beta_k D_k + \epsilon_i \dots (8)$$

Where V_{ij} = The visit rate by the 'i' th individual to the site j.

$\alpha_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_7$ = Coefficient to be estimated.

TC_{ij} = Round trip total cost to the site including travel time cost of individual 'i' when visiting site j.

Y_i = Household income of the individual 'i'.

STC = Travel cost to and from substitute site

A_i = Age of the individual visitor 'i'.

E_i = Education level of visitor 'i'.

FS_i = Family size of visitor 'i'.

D_k = Three dummy variables as follows:

D_1 = 1 if male and 0 otherwise.

D_2 = 1 if urban dweller and 0 otherwise.

D_3 = '1' if the visitor's perception about the facility is good and '0' otherwise.

ϵ_i = Error

Econometric model choice for count data

The TCM model contains a non-negative integer feature of the trip data which faces issue of the TCM demand model. These types of data are called count data. The Count Data models utilize data in which the observations are counted rather than ranked and the observations equally assume non-negative integer values (i.e. 0, 1, 2, 3 ...N). Based on the nature of distribution of data, these types of data generally suffer from either an over dispersion or under dispersion problem. The researcher has selected Poisson distribution model based on CT's Test (1990). Likewise, Akaike information Criterion and Schwarz Criterion are regarded as better model selection criteria that ensure an efficient and consistent estimator. These also suggested Poisson model as being the better choice. The dependent variable in this particular case refers to the number of trips visitors made to TBP Park.

The model for running Poisson regression is as follows:

$$Y \sim \text{Pois} (\lambda = \exp (X_i \beta)), \text{ if } Y > 0 \dots (9)$$

Where X_i the vector of the variables affecting the number of trips and β is a vector of parameters of the explanatory variables.

Based on the CT test (1990) Poisson model has been selected to estimate the model. Cameron and Trivedi (1990) developed CT's (1990) test to statistically test the over dispersion of the data. The general rule of the CT test is based on the assumption that under the Poisson model, $\{(y - E[y])^2 - E[y]\}$ has zero mean. The hypothesis setting can be expressed as:

H_0 : (The data of dependent variable is not over dispersed), i.e., $\text{Var}[y_i] = E[y_i]$

H_A : (The data of dependent variable is over dispersed), i.e., $\text{Var}[y_i] = E[y_i] + \alpha g(E[y_i])$

CT's general rule is that if: $\text{Var}[y_i]/E[y_i] > 2$ than data is over dispersed.

Based on Cameron and Trivedi (1990) criteria viz., CT's (1990) test, for over dispersion test of dependent variable, Akaike information Criterion and Schwarz Criterion, Poisson model is best suited for this study. This implies that there is no over-dispersion problem statistically. This means simple Poisson model can also give an efficient and consistent estimate. Therefore, the researcher has chosen Poisson model to estimate the regression model of this study.

Table 1. Definition of Variables in the Data Set

Variable Name	Description
TC	Round Trip Travel Cost
HHMI	Monthly Household Income of Respondent
Age	Age of Respondent
YrsSch	Years of schooling of Respondents
FS	Family size/Household size of Respondents
STC	Substitute Park Round Trip Travel Cost
DumSex	Dummy Variable, i.e., 1 if Respondent is Male, 0 if Respondent is Female
DumPR	Dummy Variable 3, i.e., 1 if Respondent is Urban Dweller, 0 if Respondent is Village Dweller
DumPQ	Dummy Variable 1, i.e., 1 if Visitors perception on Quality of Park is good 0 otherwise
WTP	Willingness to Pay
SWTP	Stated Willingness to Pay

Result and discussion

The data in table 2 exhibits socio-economic and demographic characteristics of sample respondent.

Table 2. *Socio-Economic and Demographic Characteristics of Sample*

		Respondent Visitors
SN	Variables	Quantity
1.	Mean Age (In Years)	28.47
2.	Household Size	5.88
3.	Gender	
	Male	58.3%
	Female	41.7%
4.	Place of Residence	
	Urban Dweller	59.3%
	Village Dweller	41.7%
5.	Educational Status	
	Literate	4.6%
	Basic and Primary	17.6%
	Secondary Level	42.6%
	Bachelor	27.8%
	Masters and Above	7.4%
6.	Employment Status	
	Student	27.8%
	Formally Employed	25.0%
	Unemployed	6.5%
	Retired	0.9%
	Self-employed	38.0%
	Daily Wage	1.9%
7.	How would you describe the quality of the park?	
	Good	81.5%
	Poor	18.5%
8.	Perception of respondent on current entry fee based on current facility	
	Low	15.7%
	Fair	66.7%
	High	17.6%
9.	If there is no other way but to raise the entry fee, are you ready for this?	
	Yes	89.8%
	No	10.2%

(Source: Field Survey, 2016)

Descriptive statistics

The data given in table 3 shows that the mean visitation rate is 2.44 per year per visitor. The visitor's mean TC, STC and mean monthly household income are Rs. 995, Rs. 214 and Rs. 15764 respectively. Likewise visitor's mean years of schooling are 11.86 years. Average stay time is found to be about 5 hours. Similarly, visitor's maximum Stated Willingness to Pay (SWTP) is about Rs. 33.

Table 3. *Descriptive Statistics of Key Variables*

SN	Variables	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Standard Deviation
1.	Vij	2.444	1.00	8.00	1.27765
2.	TC (in Rs.)	994.55	125.00	4825.00	688.09931
3.	HHMi (in Rs.)	15763.90	2500.00	55000.00	8896.19743
4.	Yrs Sc (in Years)	11.86	.00	17.00	3.78748
5.	Age (in Years)	28.47	16	55	9.539
6.	Average Stay hours in Park	4.58	1.00	10.00	1.61260
7.	STC (in Rs.)	213.80	.00	2000.00	478.82785
8.	SWTP (in Rs.)	32.65	.00	65.00	16.66286

Total Number of Sample Respondents 108

(Source: Field Survey, 2016)

Test of multi-collinearity

The variables were included based on the logic of the underlying economic theory. The included variables were tested for multi-collinearity. According to Loomis and Walsh (1997), an absolute value of 0.8 signifies multi-collinearity. The correlation matrix displayed in Table 4 shows no correlation higher than 0.465, which is quite lower than 0.8 indicating that the multi-collinearity does not exist within the data set. All the variables could initially be included in the analysis.

Table 4. *Correlation Matrix of Variables*

Variables	Vij	TC	HHmi	STC	Age	Yrssch	FS
Vij	1.000	-.419	.465	-.124	-.318	.077	.068
TC	-.419	1.000	-.003	.208	.204	.192	.018
HHmi	.465	-.003	1.000	.021	.106	.183	.012
STC	-.124	.208	.021	1.000	.147	.125	.022
Age	-.318	.204	.106	.147	1.000	-.139	.047
Yrssch	.077	.192	.183	.125	-.139	1.000	-.082
FS	.068	.018	.012	.022	.047	-.082	1.000

(Source: Field Survey, 2016)

Estimated result from poisson regression analysis

The estimated result of Poisson regression model is shown in table 5. In this model, only statistically significant coefficients are reported and most coefficients have the expected algebraic signs.

Table 5. *Estimated Results of Poisson Model*

Dependent Variable visit rate (V _{ij})					
SN	Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	Z-Static	Prob.
1	C	0.926	0.394	2.351915	0.018
2	TC	-0.000404*	0.000124	-3.266814	0.001
3	HHMI	0.00002*	0.000007	3.576798	0.0003
4	AGE	-0.016*	0.0074	-2.114611	0.034
5	Total number of observations 108				

(Calculated by author)

* implies coefficient significant at 5 percent significance level

R-squared	0.61
Adjusted R-squared	0.57
Darwin-Watson	2.168
Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)	3.108
Schwarz Criterion (SC)	3.356
Log Likelihood	-157.8454
LR Statistics	39.0131
Prob (LR Statistics)	0.00001

The output given above will give regression equation as follows:

$$V_{ij} = 0.926 - 0.000404TC + 0.00002HHMi - 0.00008STC - 0.016Age + \epsilon \dots \dots \dots (10)$$

Calculation of consumers surplus

According to Tikapur Municipality record, the total annual park visit in the Fiscal Year 2014/15 is 141918. As described above in the methodology section, the individual average consumer surplus could, according to Garrod and Willis (1999), be calculated using equation (3).

$$\text{Consumer surplus} = -1 / \text{Coefficient for TC} \dots \dots \dots (11)$$

Applying the results in this model gave: $\frac{-1}{-0.000404} = 2475.25$ (12)

Aggregated consumer surplus = Total Annual park Visit*2475.25 (13)

Aggregated Consumers Surplus = 141918*2475.25 = NPR 351,282,530..... (14)

The result of equation 13 puts the mean consumer surplus at NPR 2475.25. This can be interpreted as mean consumers' surplus per visitor per trip. The aggregated consumer surplus for TBP was calculated to be NPR 351,282,530 as seen in equation (14). This value seems high, and a probable cause could be the low travel cost coefficient. Even though this value seems high, it is possible that it is underestimated since the chosen method only captures the recreational value and no other parts of the total economic value. The consumer surplus has a high value. According to Garrod and Willis (1999), this is because the consumer surplus is highly sensitive to the specifications in the model. Therefore, we have to take into consideration the fact that these findings may be dynamic and differ with respect to time and conditions.

Opportunity cost of the park measured in terms of local crop production

The benefit foregone by society in terms of the next best alternative opportunity for the existence of the park is called opportunity cost in the context of this study. The opportunity cost of the park has been estimated based on the productivity of the cultivated land in and around the park. The study deals with the question of what would have been produced if the park land were cultivated for agricultural production and how much it would amount to in monetary value.

The researcher needed to take into consideration the national as well as local productivity profile in order to calculate agricultural productivity of the study area. According to Agriculture Development Strategy (ADS) 2014 of Government of Nepal, agriculture land productivity of Nepal is \$1804 per hectare per annum. But, Agriculture Service Centre, Tikapur has prepared its own land productivity profile which is suitable for this study to calculate the opportunity cost of the area surrounding TBP. Based on the profile, the researcher has calculated NPR 152500 per hectare per annum. The total area of TBP Park land is 58.0243 hectare. If the Park land were cultivated, it would yield Rs. 58.0243* NPR 152500 = NPR 8,848,706 per annum. The amount can be considered as the benefit foregone by the nation in terms of crop production for the existence of the park. The estimated opportunity cost of the park based on the crop production value in adjoining cultivated land, approximately NPR 8.85 million per annum, is the benefit forgone by the nation for the operation, maintenance and development of the park.

Calculation of benefit cost ratio

Benefits from TBP may be direct and indirect. Direct benefits include benefits from the selling of fruits like mango and lychee. Indirect benefits may include recreational benefits, income from tourists, hedonic property of the park and its surrounding area and extension of precious greenery resources. However, these benefits are beyond the scope of this study and will not be included in this research. Costs include factors like entry fee, labor costs, and salary of the park personnel, daily wages, management cost and opportunity cost.

The Tikapur Municipality revenue generated from the park as sum of entry fee, vehicle parking fee and fruit sales has reached NPR 3,936,200 for the fiscal year 2014/15 (Tikapur Municipality, 2015). The estimated recreational benefit is NPR 351,282,530. The Park has also contributed substantially to the surrounding area's real estate property based on hedonic property. All these attempts of the park cannot be underestimated in terms of the present benefit. Similarly, the future stream of benefits from the park cannot easily be anticipated. Nature conservation is a priceless regime. According to the data; status of BCR is given below.

Table 6. Calculation of Benefit Cost Ratio (BCR)

Benefit Cost Category	Particulars	Amount (in NPR)
Benefits	Estimated Recreational Benefits*	351,282,530
	Revenue from Entry Fee***	3,547,950
	Revenue from sales of fruits ***	143,000
	Revenue from vehicle Parking ***	245,250
	Total Benefit (A)	355,218,730
Costs	Salary and allowance of park staff***	2,435,700
	Repair and Maintenance cost of park***	1,664,300
	Opportunity cost of Park land**	8,848,706
	Total Cost (B)	12,948,706
	Benefit Cost Ratio (BCR) = A/B	27.43

*Calculated by Researcher based on Poisson estimation. **Calculated by Researcher based on.

*** Data from Tikapur Municipality.

$$BCR = \text{Total Benefit/Total Cost} = 355218446/12948706 = 27.43 \dots\dots\dots (15)$$

The above result of BCR given in equation (20) can be inferred as per NPR 1 cost stream has generated benefit stream of NPR. 27.43. Thus, BCR is seen to be extremely beneficial.

Conclusion

Tikapur Banglaw Park as a public recreational park provides arrays of utilities to the people of the surrounding area and the nation as a whole. There is increasing and widespread public support for public park provision in urban areas given that they provide an array of different recreational activities enhancing the citizen's quality of life. TBP has not only contributed to improving the surrounding environment by increasing greenery, reducing air, water, and noise pollution, and helping in biodiversity preservation but also generated a variety of economic benefits. The data observed in this study reveals that a vast majority of people of the far west and mid-west regions of Nepal are benefitted by TBP. Based on the survey data of this study, TBP has many recreational benefits and provides social welfare. In other words, the estimated recreational benefit is of great importance. TBP is a non-market environmental and ecological resource and an integral components for deriving recreational utility for a vast majority of people. TBP is environmental goods and service which is not traded in the usual markets; the benefits derived from this commodity exist outside the market. TBP has significantly attracted the younger people and recreational visitors from far west and mid-west regions of Nepal. Besides, TBP has contributed significantly to net value addition of the surrounding areas and economy as a whole. In other words, because of the arrival of substantial numbers of internal tourists, it has made great contribution to stimulate commercial activities in the surroundings.

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